

New European Bauhaus Call for proposals for Citizen Engagement Activities

Project Acronym: SOCIAL4FOOD

**Project title: SOCIAL farming FOR stimulating transgenerational knowledge
transfer and production of typical local FOOD**

Deliverable 3.1: CO-CREATION STRATEGY

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1. Executive summary

The SOCIAL4FOOD project aims at applying the principles of the New European Bauhaus to improve the contact between young generations and green public spaces, guided by the wisdom of the elders. Through a series of social farming activities, the project aims to stimulate the involvement of teenagers from the Town of Arsoli (including also young immigrants) in collaboratively farming and cooking a very ancient and high-quality bean typical of this town, named “fagiolina arsolana”.

This document provides information about the co-creation methodology that will be applied during all the events planned by the project. The application of this methodology is relevant for the involved target groups since it contributes to:

- *reconnecting the community with nature and regaining the sense of community and belonging to the territory;*
- *encouraging relationship building between older adults and young people breaking down generational barriers;*
- *foster a healthy and sustainable food that may become extinct in just a few short years.*

2. The co-creation methodology

A co-creation methodology has been applied in the SOCIAL4FOOD project to build the transgenerational dialogue and establish a process of contamination, inspiration, and sharing of ideas between older and younger generations.

The co-creation methodology is based on the design thinking approach which is a non-linear, iterative process which provides a solution-based approach to solving problems. The design thinking approach is extremely useful when used to tackle complex problems and it serves to understand the human needs involved, reframe the problem in human-centric ways, create numerous ideas in brainstorming sessions and adopt a hands-on approach to prototyping and testing. The approach, proposed by the Hasso Plattner Institute of Design at Stanford (2019), is composed of five stages:

- Empathize: research users' needs
- Define: state users' needs and problems
- Ideate: challenge assumptions and create ideas
- Prototype: start to create solutions
- Test: try your solutions out

The five stages of the design thinking approach have been applied during the events planned within the project, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The design thinking approach followed in the SOCIAL4FOOD project

2.1. Emphasize and define

The first stage (emphasize and define) is applied during the Open day event, in which local teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders and local farmers are involved in the (i) storytelling of experiences on the growing and cooking of the "fagiolina arsolana" and (ii) elicitation of ideas.

Specifically, two different sessions are organized to meet the needs of the different target groups: the former for adults and adolescents and the latter for children.

2.1.1. SESSION for ADULTS and ADOLESCENTS

In the first session, dedicated to adults and adolescents, the world café method is applied consisting in the following activities: collection of experiences, elicitation of ideas, sharing of ideas, and voting of ideas.

Collection of experiences

Participants are asked to answer the following triggering questions, according to their experiences:

- 1) What is your most significant experience in the GROWING of the "fagiolina arsolana" (or in the growing of agricultural products in general)? What difficulties have you encountered? What were the positive aspects?
- 2) What is your most significant experience in the COOKING of the "fagiolina arsolana" (or of the typical cuisine of Arsoli in general)? What difficulties have you encountered? What were the positive aspects?

Different groups of participants are formed, taking care to include at least one member of each target user for each group: adult, adolescent, man and women.

Each person has a maximum of 3 minutes available to tell their experience. After 20 minutes, each participant has 10 minutes to write a brief description of the experience (2-3 sentences), positive aspects and the encountered difficulties on three post-its. The post-its are attached to a poster for the final discussion.

Elicitation of ideas

Participants are asked to answer the following triggering questions, according to their ideas:

- 1) How to pass on the experience and skills necessary for the traditional growing and cooking of the "fagiolina arsolana" from local elders to adolescents?
- 2) How to stimulate the involvement of local teenagers (including young immigrants) in the collaborative growing and cooking of the "fagiolina arsolana"?

3) How would you like to organise the social farm? Who should be involved? How should the tasks be performed?

The different groups of participants appoint a spokesperson who illustrates the emerged ideas and a secretary who reports the ideas, on a sheet .

The group has a maximum of 10 minutes available for discussing and proposing ideas answering the 3 triggering questions.

Sharing of ideas

The post-it containing the different ideas that emerged from the group's discussion is put on a poster and the spokesperson of each group explains the ideas that emerged for each question.

Voting of ideas

Each participant is provided with 6 stickers to apply to the 2 ideas that he/she considers most relevant for each question (according to the level of appreciation). At the end of the vote, the most significant ideas are summarized.

2.1.2. SESSION for CHILDREN

In the second section, dedicated to children, the storytelling method is applied consisting in the following activities: storytelling of experiences with emotion definition, collection of tips, and drawings.

Storytelling of experiences

Two rounds of storytelling are organized: the former for the experiences in the cultivation of the "fagiolina arsolana" and the latter for its cooking.

In the first round, participants are divided into 3 groups; they are asked to tell their experience with the growing of garden products (in particular the "fagiolina arsolana") to the other group members. Some possible examples are given (I sowed vegetables with my father/grandfather, I attended the bean harvest event, I sowed seedlings with my teachers, etc.). After the storytelling, participants are asked to write 1-2 sentences to describe their experience. Finally, each participant is provided with 5 stickers representing smiles with emotions (very happy, happy, indifferent, sad, and very sad) and is asked to apply them to the written experience (according to their level of satisfaction).

In the second round, the same process is followed focusing on the experiences in the cooking of the "fagiolina arsolana".

Collection of tips

Participants are asked to answer the following triggering questions, according to their ideas:

1) What would you like to do to learn how to grow the "fagiolina arsolana"?

2) What would you like to do to learn how to cook the “fagiolina arsolana”?

Some possible examples are given (e.g., cultivating a vegetable garden with my companions, making a laboratory to learn, listening to the stories experienced by the elderly, etc.)

Drawings

Each participant is asked to realize a drawing for representing his/her experience.

2.2. Ideate

The second stage (ideate) is applied during the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities (green social laboratories, SOCIAL4FOOD competition, and co-creation of the social farm), in which local teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders and local farmers are involved in.

During the green social laboratories and SOCIAL4FOOD competition the “learning by doing” is applied, which is an educational approach expounded by Paulo Freire (1982). It is a hands-on learning approach in which participants interact with their environment and actually “do” the activity to adapt and learn. The learning by doing approach is composed of the following four phases, as defined by Kolb (1984): (1) having a concrete experience followed by (2) observation of and reflection on that experience which leads to (3) the formation of abstract concepts (analysis) and generalizations (conclusions) which are then (4) used to test a hypothesis in future situations, resulting in new experiences.

The four phases of the learning by doing approach applied in the project are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The learning by doing approach followed in the SOCIAL4FOOD project

A brief description of each phase is provided below.

Concrete experience

This activity starts with the knowledge transfer of cultivation techniques/cooking recipes of the “fagiolina arsolana” from the elderly to participants using storytelling techniques. Participants learn about the experience told by elderly and local farmers watching them in action. To acquire new knowledge, participants are actively engaged in cultivation/cooking activities.

Reflective observation

This phase in the learning cycle allows participants to discuss the experience with others. Communication at this stage is vital, as it allows participants to identify any discrepancies between their understanding and the experience itself. Participants are divided into groups and are invited to discuss their concrete experiences by highlighting the difficulties and the necessary improvements in the acquired knowledge.

Abstract conceptualization

In this phase, participants move from reflective observation to abstract conceptualization by classifying concepts and forming conclusions on the experience. They are asked to take notes about the concepts and knowledge acquired during the concrete experience (experience notes).

Active Experimentation

This phase in the cycle is the testing stage. Participants have a new cultivation/cooking experience in which they apply the concepts and knowledge acquired during the concrete experience phase (written in their experience notes).

2.2.1. GREEN SOCIAL LABORATORIES

Three different green social laboratories (i.e., "I learn how to grow the fagiolina", "I learn how to cook the fagiolina", and "I learn how to harvest the fagiolina") are organized by local elders and producers to transfer to adolescents, children, and interested citizens their knowledge on:

- the cultivation techniques of the “fagiolina arsolana”;
- the cooking of local recipes of the “fagiolina arsolana”;
- the harvesting techniques of the “fagiolina arsolana”.

In these laboratories, the first, second and third phases (i.e., concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization) of the learning by doing approach are implemented.

2.2.2. SOCIAL4FOOD COMPETITION

A culinary challenge among different groups composed of participants in the green social laboratories is organized during the “fagiolina festival”. Participants try their hand at cooking typical recipes by applying the concepts and knowledge acquired during the culinary laboratory.

In this competition, the last phase (i.e., active experimentation) of the learning by doing approach is implemented.

2.2.3. CO-CREATION OF THE SOCIAL FARM

Starting from the needs and ideas for the co-creation of the social farm gathered during the Open Day event organized on July 29th 2022, each participant is asked to provide some solutions about the organization of the social farm (e.g. people to involve, tasks to perform, etc.). Through a collaborative discussion, a shared solution for the co-design of the social farm is provided. Moreover, a group of “Fagiolina Ambassadors” is appointed to stimulate citizen and stakeholder engagement and participation. For the appointment, representatives for each target group involved in the project (teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders, local farmers, and citizens) are selected according to their commitment to the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities.

2.3. Prototype

The third stage (prototype) is applied during the Social farm Day in which the shared solution about the organization of the social farm (people to involve, tasks to perform, etc.) is illustrated to the audience. Afterwards, according to the proposed organization of the social farm, the “Fagiolina Ambassadors” and target participants are involved in the deforestation activities and preparation of common land for the sowing of the “fagiolina arsolana”.

2.4. Testing

During the last stage (testing) of the design thinking approach, a qualitative survey (questionnaires and interviews) for acquiring feedback from participants in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities is administered.

References

Hasso Plattner Institute (2019), “Design Thinking”, available at: <https://hpi.de/school-ofdesign-thinking/design-thinking.html>.

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